

Quick Project Guide

Compensatory Mechanisms for Vowel Articulation Induced by Vocal Fold Polyps: A Cantonese Case Study

This project contains all materials used for acoustic analysis research, organized into the following three main folders:

```
|— Chart/
|   |— Visualization charts of research results used in the article
|— Praat Scripts/
|   |— Shao_10-get_duration_and_formant/    #Formant extraction script
|   |— Xiong_xzy_draw_vowel/              #Vowel plot generation script
|— vowel_acoustic_analysis/
|   |— data/
|   |   |— data_iau.xlsx                    # Raw acoustic measurements
|   |   |— nonparametric_descriptive.xlsx
|   |   |— nonparametric_results.xlsx
|   |— scripts/
|   |   |— kruskal_dunn_iau.py              # Non-parametric statistical analysis
|   |   |— physiological_parameters_iau.py  # Physiological parameter calculation
|   |   |— environment.yml                  # Conda environment configuration
|   |   |— requirements.txt                 # Python package dependencies
|   |   |— README.md                       # Detailed package documentation
|   |— results/                             # Analysis outputs
|   |   |— nonparametric_descriptive.xlsx   # Descriptive statistics (median, IQR)
|   |   |— nonparametric_results.xlsx      # Statistical test results
|   |   |— physiological_parameters_results.xlsx
```

1. Chart Folder

- (1) Content: All charts used in the article.
- (2) Includes: Vocal polyp diagrams, vowel plots.

2. Praat Scripts Folder

- (1) Content: Two Praat script packages used in the research.
- (2) Includes:
 - a. Formant and duration extraction script: *Shao_10-get_duration_and_formant/*
 - b. Vowel plot generation script: *Xiong_xzy_draw_vowel/*

3. vowel_acoustic_analysis Folder

- (1) Content: Core code package for data statistical analysis and parameter calculation.
- (2) Includes: Formant data, Python analysis scripts, environment configuration files, result files.
- (3) Detailed usage: Please refer to the README.md file inside this folder.